

Dafne Documentation

Version 1.3-alpha

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Preamble

Dafne is a program for the segmentation of medical images, specifically MR images, that includes advanced deep learning models for an automatic segmentation. The user has the option of refining the automated results, and the software will learn from the improvements and modify its internal models accordingly. In order to continuously improve the performance, the deep learning modules are stored in a central server location (see section Deep Learning below)

License

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Authorship

Dafne has been developed in a joint effort by the University of Basel, the Basel University Hospital, and the Mondino Foundation. See the About page for detailed authorship information.

The main developers currently are: Francesco Santini, Jakob Wasserthal, and Abramo Agosti. Medical supervision by Anna Pichiecchio.

The project is supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation, Spark Project #CRSK-3_196515

Third-party code

Dafne depends on a number of third-party libraries, released under GPL or compatible licenses. For a full list of dependencies, please refer to the `requirements.txt` and the `README.md` files in the github repository.

Download and installation

Dafne is written in pure Python, and is thus multi-platform. The code and the distributable binaries are accessible on Github.

Source installations

Dafne is compatible with Python 3.8+.

Note for source installations

Dafne uses flexidep for advanced control of dependencies. This means that some dependencies will be installed at the first run of this program. Please make sure that you have proper internet access the first time you run Dafne, so that they can be installed. This obviously does not apply for binary installation.

Pip installation

Dafne is available on the PyPi repository. You can install it with

```
pip install dafne
```

Dafne should be available for execution from the command line by typing `dafne`.

Davelopment installation

The Dafne repository can be cloned with the command:

```
git clone https://github.com/dafne-imaging/dafne.git
```

It can then be installed in editable mode (for development) with

```
cd dafne
pip install -e .
```

Dafne will then be available on the command line as in the pip installation. Alternatively, the dependencies can be installed with

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

and the program executed with

```
python dafne
```

The deep learning management is done in a separate repository, which can also be cloned and installed in editable mode. Do this *before installing Dafne dependencies*:

```
git clone https://github.com/dafne-imaging/dafne-dl.git
cd dafne-dl
pip install -e .
```

Binary installations

Windows 10

In the Github releases page, an installer for Windows generated with PyInstaller and InnoSetup is provided. The installation package is created under Windows 10 version 20H2 and might not work with earlier versions of Windows. Before installing, please make sure that the Visual C Runtime is installed. If unsure, you can download and install it directly from this page (direct link to the installer)

Mac OS binary installation

In the Github releases page, packaged versions for Mac OS (86_x64 packaged under Catalina and amd64 packaged under Ventura) generated with PyInstaller are available. Make sure to download the version corresponding to your architecture! If you are unsure, try the arm64 version first, and if it doesn't work, try the x86_64 version.

From this release, the Mac version is shipped as a standard (code-signed) Mac application packaged inside a dmg file. Download the dmg file, double-click on it, and copy the "Dafne" App to you Applications folder.

Linux binary installation

Dafne is also released in binary version for Linux. It is packaged as a single-file application with PyInstaller. Just download the appropriate binary file (`dafne_linux_<VERSION>`), make it executable by running (substitute `<VERSION>` with the version code, e.g. `1.1-alpha7`):

```
chmod +x dafne_linux_<VERSION>
```

and run it as any other linux program.

```
./dafne_linux_<VERSION>
```

Main interface

The main interface of Dafne is composed of two windows:

- the **Toolbox**, where the menus and the commands are;
- the **Image Window**, where the dataset is visualized.

Image loading and viewing

Open a dataset from the menu **File -> Load data...** To open a DICOM dataset, navigate to the folder and click on any dicom file. The entire folder will be loaded. After selecting a dataset, a popup window will ask to choose the classification for this dataset, which will determine which deep learning model to use for the automatic segmentation. If no appropriate deep learning model is available, choose **None**. You will be able to change this afterwards, also on a per-slice basis.

Once the dataset is open, window the image by using the **right mouse button**. You can scroll through the images with the **scroll wheel** or with the **arrow keys**.

Use the buttons **Pan** and **Zoom** in the interface to adjust the magnification.

Deep learning

The main feature of Dafne is the possibility of doing **automatic segmentation** using **deep learning models**.

Dafne uses **incremental learning** and **federated learning** to continuously adapt the models to the need of our users. This means that when you perform a segmentation, initially it will not be perfect. You will then have the chance to refine it. When you are satisfied with your dataset, you will export your ROI masks (see below). During this export procedure, the software automatically learns from your refined segmentation and sends the updated model back to our servers. This is why the export procedure takes some time. We will automatically integrate your updated model with the models of our other users, so you will always receive the most accurate predictor. You can also manually perform the incremental learning from the Tools menu (see below)

It is important to say that **your data never leave your computer** (unless you explicitly want to), so you don't have to worry about privacy and data safety.

Currently, we offer two deep learning models:

1. The **thigh** model, which identifies 12 muscles of the thigh.
2. The **leg** model, which identifies 6 muscles of the leg.

Both models are pretrained on **axial proton-density-weighted in-phase gradient echo images** (in the picture, an example). Best results will be achieved with similar protocols; however, the model will adapt in the future depending on the user base.

Each model, by default, is meant to work on both limbs at the same time. Select the **Right** or **Left** model variants to segment single-limb datasets.

In order to use the deep learning models, you will have to obtain a **personalized API key** that gives you access to the server. See the “Get Dafne” page to obtain it. Once you have the key, you will have to open the preferences (from **Tools->Preferences...**) and set the relevant parameters: model location to **Remote** and your API key in the provided space.

Another relevant setting is the checkbox “Separate L/R in autosegment”. When checked, the left and right limb will generate different ROIs; otherwise, the same muscle on the two different sides will belong to the same ROI.

The toolbox

The tools available in Dafne are displayed in the **Segmentation Toolbox** window. This window changes according to the current edit mode (*mask mode* and *contour mode*, which we'll see in a moment). However, there is some common functionality to the two modes, which we can see in this image.

Figure 1: Toolbox main

The top box shows the classification of the current slice. It can be changed by simply changing the content of the dropdown box. The button “All” sets the classification for all the slices in the dataset.

The ROI box shows the currently active ROI, with a button to add a new ROI and another to delete the current ROI. **Beware! Deleting a ROI will delete it from ALL the slices in the dataset!**

In contour edit mode, each ROI is divided in subrois, because each ROI mask can be divided into multiple contours. Adding or deleting a subroi will only affect the current slice.

Below the ROI box, the **Autosegment** button will perform automatic segmentation using the deep learning model (see above). A dialog will open to allow you to perform the segmentation on a set of slices.

At the bottom of the toolbox, there is a registration section (which is only visible if SimpleITK with the SimpleElastix extension is present, see <https://simpleelastix.github.io/> or here for precompiled packages). From this section, propagation of the current ROI to the next/previous slice is performed, by means of nonrigid registration. Calculating the registration across the slices can be time consuming, but the registration information is stored automatically in your image folder (in a file named `transforms.p`), so subsequent operations will be

faster. We suggest you use **Calculate transforms** to precalculate the transforms for the whole dataset. It will take some time, but it will speed up subsequent operations. Please notice that you will not be able to interact with Dafne while the calculation is in progress. As an alternative, you can use the *offline transform calculator*, also provided with Dafne and accessible either from the menu, or as a separate program (see below).

Edit modes

Dafne has two edit modes to modify ROIs: the *mask mode* and the *contour mode*. In the *mask mode*, you can “paint” on the image with a brush, whereas in *contour mode* you can define a contour through control points. We suggest the use of mask mode to refine autosegmented datasets, and contour mode to define new ROIs; however, different options are available in different modes. You can easily switch from one mode to the other in the segmentation toolbox.

Mask edit mode

In mask edit mode, you can paint on your image as you would in an image editing program like Photoshop. The active ROI is shown in red, while non-active ones are shown in blue. If you right-click on the image, the ROIs disappear so you can better see the boundaries (all these settings are customizable in the preferences).

Figure 2: Mask Edit

Clicking on **Paint** or **Erase** allows you to add or remove bits to the current ROI. By selecting **Intensity aware**, the brush will only paint over or erase voxels whose intensity is close to the central voxel where you initially started painting.

The **Brush** shape and size determines how the painting is done. You will see a patch of color where the mouse pointer is to show the portion of the image that will be affected. In *Erase* mode, a checkbox allows you to affect all the ROIs in the image, for example to remove spurious elements outside the overall region of interest. **Note:** if the patch is not visible, make sure that a) paint or erase are selected b) you are not in zoom/pan mode c) the image window is active by clicking on it.

As a shorthand for paint/erase, you can hold your **shift** or **control** button respectively.

Lastly, you can also grow or shrink the mask, or remove small areas or holes by clicking on the appropriate buttons on the toolbox.

You can change the opacity of the masks on the fly with the “Opacity” slider.

Contour edit mode

In contour edit mode, you can draw contours by defining handle points, and the software will interpolate between them. This is useful for accurately defining borders of new ROIs. In this mode, the same ROI may have different subROIs. This means that the different closed contours will then be merged to calculate the mask. When contours overlap, the difference is taken (technically, it’s a XOR operation). The active subroi is depicted in red,

other subrois belonging to the same ROI (which will be merged) are depicted in yellow, and other ROIs are depicted in blue.

Figure 3: Contour Edit

The small red circles are the handles of the contour. Similarly to paint and erase in mask mode, **Add/Move** and **Remove** modify the handles accordingly. **Clear** removes all the handles from the current subroi (while leaving the subroi active). Conversely the - button next to the subroi menu deletes the subroi altogether.

The **Translate** mode allows moving the whole contour, while **Rotate** allows rotation around the center of mass.

Mask interpolation and registration

The bottom part of the toolbar is dedicated to mask interpolation and propagation through registration.

Figure 4: Mask interpolation and registration

The **Interpolate** button generates a mask or contour for the current slice based on slices segmented above and below. Note: this only works for the currently selected ROI.

Either simple linear interpolation of the contour, registration-based interpolation, or a combination of both can be selected.

The **Interpolate block** button will apply the desired interpolation to all slices between two already-segmented slices.

In the **Registration** group, forward and backward propagation based on nonrigid cross-slice registration is implemented. For simplicity, the shortcuts **n** for forward propagation, and **b** for backward propagation can be used.

In case you want to use registration-based features, it is very much recommended to precalculate the transforms between the slices, either by using the **Calculate transforms** button, or, asynchronously, with the transform calculator (see below).

Menus

Dafne has three main menus: the **File** menu, the **Tools** menu, and the **ROI** menu.

The File menu

This menu contains the input/output options.

Figure 5: File Menu

- **Load data** will load a new dataset. Currently, Dicom, Nifti, and Numpy formats are supported.
- **Reorient data** will reorient the loaded dataset along a different axis.
- **Import/Export ROI file** will load or save ROI information in an internal Dafne format (with extension .p). **A ROI file can only be used with the same dataset used for its creation** or with an identical dataset (in terms of size and orientation). This is in contrast to the mask import (see below) Note that Dafne will periodically save files in this format in the data directory. Make sure to clean the directory periodically, as they can grow large.
- **Import masks** will import binary masks from dicom or numpy files. If the imported masks are DICOM, the software will attempt to align the dataset with the currently loaded one, so it is a way to transfer ROIs across different acquisitions. **It might take some time** especially if the currently loaded dataset is a 2D multislice dataset. When loading multiple masks saved as DICOM, you can choose the *Import multiple masks* functionality. You can then select the folder containing all the ROI subfolders and they will be loaded at the same time. This is much more efficient than loading a single ROI one by one.
- **Save masks** will export the ROIs to disk, in numpy or DICOM format. In case of DICOM format, the same dicom headers of the loaded dataset will be used, and new folders with ROI names will be created. **Note:** this is a **very important** operation, because the model learns every time masks are exported. Without exporting masks, no model improvement is performed. This is also the reason why this operation takes some time (depending on the performance of your computer). The masks can also be saved in *compact* format, which means that all the labels are compacted into a single image and each gray level corresponds to a label. Together with the exported dataset, a *legend* file in CSV format will be saved. This file is also important (with the correct naming) to import the labels.
- **Upload data** will send the current loaded data with the ROI information to our servers. **!!Use with extreme care!!** You don't need to send your data to us, but you might wish to do so to help us improve the program. **Make sure that you have the right to do so!** We take no responsibility for any breach of local regulations that you might incur.

The Tools menu

In the tools menu, statistics calculation and the preference editor are located.

- **Improve model** will perform an automatic model improvement step using the already-segmented data, so that subsequent segmentations are more accurate. A minimum of 5 slices are required for this step to work.
- **Calculate statistics** will produce a csv (tabular) data file with some statistics regarding the drawn ROIs. What is saved is:

Figure 6: Tools Menu

- The ROI name
- The number of slices in which the ROI is defined
- The total number of voxels in the ROI
- The average value of the image in the ROI
- The standard deviation
- The 0th percentile (minimum value)
- The 25th percentile
- The 50th percentile (median)
- The 75th percentile
- The 100th percentile (maximum)

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	roi_name	slices	voxels	mean	standard_deviation	perc_0	perc_25	perc_50	perc_75	perc_100
2	Vastus Lateralis_R	3	3947	254.25995	43.342716	23	246	262	275	393
3	Vastus Lateralis_L	3	4095	232.46642	53.294113	26	197	231	274	352
4	Vastus Medialis_R	3	2258	229.15811	41.012035	60	199	234	263	316
5	Vastus Medialis_L	3	1808	226.46184	33.28146	57	206	230	250	307
6	Vastus Intermedius_R	3	2554	246.09044	28.94973	51	235	248	263	320

Figure 7: Stats

- **PyRadiomics** will produce a csv file with texture analysis features from the Pyradiomics package (if available).
- **Open transform calculator** will open a tool that allows an offline calculation of the nonrigid transforms between slices, in order to speed up subsequent propagation operations. A screenshot of the tool is shown below. Select a folder with DICOM files and click on “*Calculate transforms*” to start the calculation. The transforms will be stored at the end in an internal Dafne format, in the same folder as the dicom files. For performance reasons, we suggest you to start this tool directly as a separate executable (`calc_transforms.py` in the source installation, or `calc_transforms.exe` in the windows compiled installation)
- **Preferences** will open the preference editor.
- **Restore factory settings** will restore the default Dafne preferences.

The ROI menu

This menu allows some operations on ROIs.

- **Copy/Rename** will make a copy of a ROI, or change its name. A copy is performed unless the *Make copy* checkbox is unchecked.
- **Combine** will perform boolean operations over two ROIs. The output ROI will be replaced with the result of the operation. If you wish to create a new ROI, select *Specify a different name* in the **Output ROI** field and write the name in the text box. The available operations are:
 - Union: The two ROIs are combined (*OR*)
 - Subtraction: The second ROI is subtracted from the first (*AND NOT*)

Figure 8: Offline transform calculator

Figure 9: ROI menu

Figure 10: Copy/Rename

- Intersection: The common area between two ROIs is retained (*AND*)
- Exclusion: The non-overlapping portions of the two ROIs are retained (*XOR*)

Figure 11: Combine

- **Multiple combine** allows boolean operations on multiple ROIs at the same time.
- **Remove overlap** will remove the overlap between the current ROI and the others by deleting the overlapping areas of the other ROIs. It is useful when correcting misassignment of areas of the image to the wrong ROI.

Keyboard shortcuts

Some keyboard shortcuts are available for convenience.

Command	Key(s)
Previous Image	[Left Arrow], [Up Arrow]
Next Image	[Right Arrow], [Down Arrow]
Paint/Add/Move	[Shift]
Erase/Delete	[Ctrl/Cmd]
Propagate Forward	n
Propagate Back	b
Reduce Brush Size	-, y, z, [Ctrl/Cmd]+[Scroll Down]
Increase Brush Size	+, x, [Ctrl/Cmd]+[Scroll Up]
Remove ROI Overlap	r
Undo	[Ctrl]+z
Redo	[Ctrl]+y
Go to image	[Ctrl]+g

Bug reporting and troubleshooting

Please report bugs on Github or through the contact page of the site.

When reporting a bug, please include the log files called `dafne_output.log` and `dafne_error.log` (make sure that no sensitive information is contained inside!). The log files can be found at the following locations (replace `<user>` with your user name):

- **Windows:** `C:\Users\<user>\AppData\Local\Dafne-imaging\Dafne\Logs`
- **Mac:** `/Users/<user>/Library/Logs/Dafne/`
- **Linux:** `/home/<user>/.cache/Dafne/Log/`